

Study of Heteroatomic Constituents in Darius Crude

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The heavy ends of petroleum are important contributors to future petroleum requirements. Little information is available on the nature of non-hydrocarbon constituents in this fraction, particularly those containing two heteroatoms in the same molecule. Isolation of a bi-hetero compound is reported from the 300-470° fraction of Darius crude. Its structure has been elucidated using spectral techniques.

THE distillable fraction of petroleum is composed mainly of hydrocarbons with variable amounts of sulphur as principal, and lesser amounts of nitrogen and oxygen compounds as other constituents. Despite their smaller concentration, the nitrogen, oxygen and sulphur compounds play an important role in the science of petroleum. They poison many refining catalysts and cause considerable deposits in finished products such as gasoline and jet fuels¹⁻¹². A knowledge of nature of these hetero-compounds should prove useful in the development of processes for their removal and of additives for their control. Although the composition of hydrocarbons and sulphur compounds in petroleum¹³ has been understood in general terms for about 25 years, a similar understanding of nitrogen and oxygen compounds has unfolded only during the past few years. Little information, however, is available on the presence of compounds containing both sulphur and nitrogen in the same molecule in petroleum. La Lau¹⁴ and Jewell *et al*¹⁵ first revealed the presence of bihetero-aromatics in heavy gas oil.

The compound discussed in the present paper was isolated by repeated column, inverse phase dry column and thin layer chromatography^{16,17} (Fig. 1). The structure of the compound was elucidated by the combined use of its uv, ir, nmr and mass spectral data.

Structure elucidation :

The ir spectrum of the compound showed bands characteristic of secondary amino (a medium band of NH stretching vibration at 3400 cm⁻¹), ester (medium to strong bands at 1732 cm⁻¹ of $\nu_{C=O}$, 1260 cm⁻¹ of ν_{O-C-O} and at 1030 cm⁻¹ of ν_{C-O-C}), sulphide (weak to medium band at 750 cm⁻¹ of ν_{C-S} and a weak to medium doublet at 733 and 723 cm⁻¹ suggestive of sulphur in a ring system), and aromatic groups¹⁸⁻²² (weak to medium band at 1595 cm⁻¹). Absence of bands in the 3040 cm⁻¹ region (aromatic ν_{CH}) suggested the presence of completely substituted aromatic ring, while the doublet at 722 and 733 cm⁻¹ was typical of a sulphur atom in the ring system²³.

Fig. 1

The nmr spectrum of the compound (Fig. 2) showed a broad multiplet of four protons between 3.36-4.56 ppm suggesting that the protons were situated between two electronegative groups²⁴ while the four protons between 1.80-2.70 ppm were assigned to the benzylic protons^{20,24,25}. The regions between 0.80-1.13 and 1.27-1.60 ppm represented methyl and methylene protons of alkyl group^{20,21,24,26}.

It thus appears from the above spectral data that the compound contained a completely substituted aromatic ring with only four benzylic protons. Such a small number of protons on a completely substituted benzene ring could only be visualized if the aromatic ring was flanked by

Fig. 2. ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of component in CCl_4 .

The mass spectrum of the compound showed parent and base ion peaks at m/e 507 and 43, respectively. The odd mass number of the parent ion peak suggested that the molecule contained odd number of nitrogen atoms. With one nitrogen, one sulphur and two oxygen atoms [of the ester group (ir)] in the molecule, a molecular formula which accounted for all the functional groups as well as total protons in the nmr was $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{45}\text{SNO}_2$ suggesting 11 unsaturations in the molecule. Out of these eleven unsaturations, ten were accounted for in structure I. The remaining one unsaturation was that of the carbonyl of the ester group.

One of the peaks in the mass spectrum was at m/e 324 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{27}$). This fragment ion lost CO_2 to give a peak at m/e 280 ($324 - 44$). Hence,

a $-\text{C}(=\text{O})\text{OC}_{18}\text{H}_{27}$ side chain was attached to the basic skeleton which contained in it the $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{NS}$ part of the molecule ($\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{45}\text{SNO}_2 - \text{CO}_2\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{27}$). The $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{NS}$ - partial formula could be explained if 4 of the periferal rings in structure I were five membered and the $-\text{NH}$ group was adjacent to sulphur atom in a six membered periferal ring as in structure II.

saturated periferal rings, one of the benzylic carbon being tertiary and one benzylic proton adjacent to sulphur or nitrogen so as to appear down field. The following partial structure (I) satisfied the above data.

II

Schemes 1-3 explain the various fragment ions formed in the mass spectrum. The above structure

was completely in agreement with the ir and nmr data.

Conclusion :

The compound discussed in the present paper was isolated by repeated liquid chromatography of Darius crude (300-470° fraction). The uv, ir, nmr and mass spectral data of the compound revealed its heterocyclic nature with a central aromatic ring flanked on all sides by saturated periferal rings. Both nitrogen and sulphur were present in one of these rings.

Scheme 2

Scheme 3

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